

VASEACAD

NEWSLETTER

Issue 1 | July 2026

One year of collaboration, innovation and progress towards a
circular blue bioeconomy

Sustainable Blue
Economy Partnership

Funded by
the European Union

WELCOME

Welcome to the first edition of the VASEACAD Newsletter, where we share the latest developments from our journey towards a more sustainable and circular blue bioeconomy.

Every year, seafood processing generates large quantities of heads, bones, skins, trimmings and other by-products. Although these materials contain valuable proteins, oils and bioactive compounds, much of this biomass is still underused or directed towards low-value applications.

VASEACAD (Valorising Seafood Side Streams, Residues, Unwanted Catches and Discards for the Production of Bioactive Protein Hydrolysates and High Added-Value Biomolecules) is changing this approach. Over the next three years, the project will develop innovative and sustainable ways to recover valuable compounds from seafood side streams and transform them into ingredients for food, feed and health applications.

Funded by the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership and co-funded by the European Commission together with the national funding agencies of the participating countries, VASEACAD brings together ten organisations from seven European countries, combining expertise from research, industry and SMEs.

This first newsletter looks back at the project's first year, highlighting key milestones, events and achievements that have laid the foundations for the work ahead.

PROJECT MILESTONES

VASEACAD Officially Launched

1 July 2025

VASEACAD officially began on 1 July 2025, bringing together ten organisations from seven European countries to develop innovative ways of transforming seafood processing side streams into valuable products for food, feed and health applications. Over the next three years, the consortium will work to improve resource efficiency, reduce waste and support the transition towards a circular blue bioeconomy.

→ Read the full story [here](#)

Partners Meet in Dublin for the Kick-off Meeting

6–7 November 2025

The VASEACAD consortium gathered at Technological University Dublin for the project's official kick-off meeting. Partners discussed the scientific roadmap, coordinated the first project activities and strengthened collaboration across the consortium. The meeting also included a visit to BioAtlantis' production facilities and Banna Strand, offering valuable insights into industrial processing and strengthening collaboration among project partners.

→ Read the full story [here](#)

Consortium Reviews First-Year Progress

15 June 2026

One year after its launch, the consortium met online to review progress across all work packages and coordinate the next phase of the project. Discussions focused on scientific developments, preparations for pilot-scale demonstrations, stakeholder engagement and future project activities, ensuring VASEACAD remains on track to achieve its objectives.

→ [Read the full story here](#)

High -Value Products

Omega-3 Oils

Neutraceuticals

Fish Protein
Ingredients

Bioactive
Hydrolysates

SHARING OUR WORK

VASEACAD Presented on Turkish National Radio

2 December 2025

Researchers from Karadeniz Technical University introduced VASEACAD to listeners of TRT Trabzon Radio, explaining how the project aims to transform seafood side streams into valuable products while supporting more sustainable fisheries and aquaculture. The interview highlighted both the project's scientific ambitions and the contribution of the Turkish team.

→ [Read the full story here](#)

VASEACAD Presented to the European Commissioner for Fisheries and Oceans

19 December 2025

During a visit to Frederick University, European Commissioner for Fisheries and Oceans, Prof. Costas Kadis, was introduced to VASEACAD and its contribution to sustainable aquaculture and the circular blue bioeconomy. The meeting showcased how European research is helping create new value from seafood processing by-products while supporting innovation and environmental sustainability.

→ [Read the full story here](#)

VASEACAD at the 2nd Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership Symposium

10–12 February 2026

VASEACAD participated in the 2nd Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership Symposium in Bucharest, where the project was presented to researchers, policymakers, industry representatives and funding organisations from across Europe. The event provided an excellent opportunity to exchange knowledge, strengthen collaborations and explore new opportunities for innovation within the blue bioeconomy.

→ [Read the full story here](#)

GROWING OUR IMPACT

2021 United Nations Decade
2030 of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

VASEACAD Recognised as a UN Ocean Decade Action

23 March 2026

A major milestone for the project came with its official endorsement as a UN Ocean Decade Action under the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030). This recognition places VASEACAD within a global network of initiatives working to deliver practical, science-based solutions that support healthier oceans and a more sustainable blue economy.

→ Read the full story [here](#)

VASEACAD

Building VASEACAD Identity

March 2026

During its first year, VASEACAD established a strong communication platform to support knowledge sharing and stakeholder engagement. The project launched its visual identity, website, brochure, infographic, LinkedIn and Facebook pages, creating the foundations for communicating project activities and results to researchers, industry, policymakers and the wider public.

→ Visit VASEACAD [website](#)

→ See VASEACAD [brochure](#)

→ See VASEACAD [infographic](#)

Meet the Coordinator: Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)

The Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR) is one of Europe's leading marine research organisations, bringing together expertise in oceanography, marine biology, biotechnology and aquaculture to address some of the most pressing challenges facing our oceans.

Operating under the supervision of the Greek General Secretariat for Research and Innovation, HCMR combines world-class scientific facilities with decades of experience in translating research into practical solutions for society.

Within VASEACAD, the project is coordinated by HCMR's Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC) through the Fish Nutrition and Omics Technologies (FiNuOm) Laboratory. The institute is internationally recognised for its research in fish nutrition, aquaculture innovation, marine biotechnology and sustainable feed development, with more than 1,800 scientific publications and collaborations spanning over 70 countries worldwide.

As project coordinator, HCMR leads the overall management of VASEACAD while playing a central scientific role in developing innovative aquafeeds and validating novel ingredients derived from seafood side streams. The team formulates and produces experimental fish diets, carries out feeding trials with gilthead seabream, evaluates fish growth, health and welfare, and assesses how new dietary ingredients can improve resource efficiency and support more sustainable aquaculture. These activities are essential for demonstrating how seafood processing by-products can be transformed into valuable resources within a circular blue bioeconomy.

Meet the HCMR Team

VASEACAD brings together a multidisciplinary team from HCMR, combining expertise in project management, fish nutrition, aquaculture, analytical chemistry and marine biotechnology.

Dr Ioannis (Yannis) Kotzamanis is the VASEACAD Project Coordinator and Research Director at IMBBC. With more than 28 years of experience in fish nutrition and aquaculture, his research focuses on developing sustainable feed ingredients and understanding how nutrition influences fish growth, health and welfare using advanced omics technologies. In VASEACAD, he oversees the overall coordination of the consortium while leading the development and evaluation of innovative aquafeeds.

Dr George Triantaphyllidis, Senior Expert and Research Fellow, serves as Project Manager. Bringing extensive experience from more than 60 European research and innovation projects, he coordinates the project's twinning and demonstration activities and supports collaboration between partners to maximise the project's impact.

Mr Efstratios Roussos is a researcher specialising in fish nutrition and sustainable aquafeeds. His work focuses on developing experimental diets, conducting feeding trials and analysing how alternative ingredients influence fish growth and health. Within VASEACAD, he contributes to feed production, biochemical analyses and scientific reporting.

Ms Vasiliki Ilia is an experienced ichthyologist with extensive expertise in Mediterranean aquaculture species and biochemical analysis of fish feeds and tissues. In the project, she supports the feeding trials and laboratory analyses that evaluate the nutritional performance of the experimental diets.

→ [Read more information here](#)

LOOKING AHEAD

The second year of VASEACAD will focus on moving from laboratory research towards pilot-scale demonstrations and strengthening collaboration with stakeholders across Europe.

Among the activities planned for the coming months are:

- Preparation of pilot-scale processing activities using SINTEF Ocean's Mobile Sea Lab.
- Continued development and evaluation of bioactive protein hydrolysates.
- Expansion of stakeholder engagement activities and establishment of the project's Advisory Board.
- Participation in scientific conferences and dissemination events.
- Publication of the next project newsletter and new website articles.

As the project progresses, VASEACAD will continue sharing its results with researchers, industry, policymakers and the wider public, contributing to a more sustainable and circular blue bioeconomy.

STAY CONNECTED

Stay up to date with the latest project news, research highlights, events and achievements as we work towards a more sustainable and circular blue bioeconomy.

 Website - www.vaseacad.eu

 Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61586148932368>

 LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vaseacad/>

 Zenodo Community https://zenodo.org/communities/vaseacad_sbep2024-997/

 Contact - info@blueecotech.eu

Become part of the VASEACAD Community
 Receive project news, event invitations and collaboration opportunities.
 Scan to join!

Partners

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